

HOMOEOPATHIC CHATBOT: A SIMPLIFIED AND ACCURATE CASE-RECEIVING AND REPERTORISING APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Chatbot is a computer software that helps to interact among people through the internet. Existing homoeopathic software serves as a support system for practitioners in remedy selection following a rigorous search for rubrics from clinical interviews, which they practice manually using their intelligence and careful understanding of symptomatology. To investigate the viability of the Chatbot application in repertorization using the "Head" Chapter of Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics Repertory as an example. Incorporating the most advanced technology for modernizing homeopathic repertories to achieve accuracy and simplified case-receiving process which helps in the management of time for both physician and patient. These studies were found by searching the Google Scholar and PubMed databases for studies that examined how artificial intelligence aids in the development of chatbots, how it works, how it can be more user-friendly for patients and doctors when taking cases, and how it is employed for easy and fast case-taking. This article discussed and examined how artificial intelligence aids in the development of chatbots, how it works, and how it can be more user-friendly for patients and doctors when taking cases. And quick repertorization for homeopathic physicians which helps in the selection of the most similitum.

KEYWORDS: Chatbot, Artificial Intelligence, Homoeopathic Software, Homoeopathic Repertory,
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INTRODUCTION

A chatbot is regarded as "computer software aiming to simulate human-to-human interaction, particularly over the Internet." It uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) and sentiment analysis to communicate in human language with users or other chatbots via text or voice. Chatbots can be utilized in a variety of industries, including education, business and e-commerce, health, and entertainment, as well as to emulate human interaction and delight people ¹.

BBCR is primarily established on the Doctrine of Complete Symptoms and Concomitants, the Pathological Doctrine in general, and the Doctrine of Causation and Time. Dr.Boger's school of thought holds that three variables influence the patient's individualization: cause, concomitants, and modalities ².

EXISTING METHODS OF DOCTOR-PATIENT INTERACTION AND REPERTORISATION:

Medical chatbots:

The main advantage of a medical chatbot is that it is a text-to-text appointment bot that answers patients' medical difficulties in a chat and delivers a personalized recommendation based on the symptoms. The Chatbot is then designed to describe medication as a pharmaceutical dosage dependent on the age of the recipient. A dedicated device that can answer all medication questions and is designed to work in multiple applications. Effective Illness Diagnosis Based on Symptoms Is simple to incorporate and update based on feedback and knowledge for a safer existence ³. To protect the population against coronavirus infections, several countries established numerous chatbots to address the nCOV-19 by various names, which may address complaints, preventions, and daily case updates like the WHO nCOV-19 Launched Bot, german 'fight COVID messenger bot', Bangladesh developed an nCOV-19 information bot. In India, the Aarogya Setu smartphone app was recently developed to raise awareness of nCOV-19 with the use of a chatbot ⁴.

Homeopathic software's:

Existing homeopathic software supports practitioners in remedy selection after a rigorous search for rubrics from clinical interviews, manually with their intelligence and careful knowledge of patient symptoms. Computer use is well suited for the field of homeopathy, especially when choosing medications. A well-known software is RADAR (Rapid Aid to Drug Aided Research) for Windows. The Chief Medical Officer's vision for the future NHS states that the physician of the future will be computer literate and work in a paperless workplace. There are seven analysis techniques, making it rapid and individualized. The VES (Vithoukas Expert System), which is arguably the next-best thing to always have the Master with you, is also included in the package.⁵ One of the top programs, Radar Opus, has several features that are crucial for doctors, including materia medica, a repertory, and patient files. The development of online professional homeopathy education: Using web technologies to enhance case taking and homeopathic prescription performance. The most recent classical homeopathic online expert system is called Vithoukas Compass. Homeopaths will be able to quickly communicate cases and other information via a secure internet application thanks to Vithoukas Compass, which intends to establish a worldwide homeopathic web-based community "center".⁶ J. Fichet claims that the advent of computer-assisted medicine has marked a turning point for homeopathy. According to their conception of health, being in perfect harmony with the vital energy that drives the human body means being in good health. The sick person displays morbid symptoms in both mind and body, showing a struggle to recover health as a result of an unbalanced energetic condition. Data structures based on effective codification may make information appear to be highly organized⁷. The fuzzy sets theory is a more recent technique that has been used in medicine. An intriguing method for dealing with the representation of inaccurate medical entities in expert systems by fuzzy set theory. The quality of the rubrics chosen has a significant impact on the homeopaths' rubrics. The main resource for information on homeopathy is Materia Medica. Despite having access to a wealth of knowledge, homeopaths frequently recommend simple treatments. Medical data analysis employs machine learning technology. A technique used in artificial intelligence that resembles human thought is fuzzy logic. The severity of the symptoms is evaluated on a scale of 1 to 4. Intensities 1 and 2 refer to symptoms that are overtly present and that are extremely frequent or intense^{8, 9}.

CURRENT DEVICES CITED POTENTIAL DOWNSIDES:

The bulk of available software is designed to make the process of repertorization easier because the physician must undertake his or her analysis, evaluation, and insertion of the rubric. Only a few software, such as KENBO, KENTIAN, and HOMPAT, do automatic case processing as soon as required data from a patient is acquired. However, there is still the issue of time spent gathering patient information. When there is a need to meet the demand of a large number of patients and swiftly attend to each individual, the risk of losing critical information in the interview reports increases. When using standardized forms or questionnaires for interviews, the queries to patients are not adequately specialized to portray individuals' distinctive symptoms, lowering the interview's effectiveness. While reporting murmurings, the individual may unintentionally jump from one subject to another, resulting in unexplained entire symptoms and misdirecting the cure determination. Some patients express their groans so swiftly that a doctor believes it is difficult to notice and grasp them on time. Because of manual repertorization, the record-keeping process is difficult, and stored records may be lost or misplaced.

NEED FOR SMART WAY SOLUTION FOR PATIENT INTERACTION:

The chatbot communicates with a patient by holding a conference, interpreting their main complaints in normal English, and submitting reports to specialists for further action. Homeopathic Chatbot assists in obtaining detailed chief complaints, saving the Homeopathic practitioner a significant amount of time. It also aids in the collection of minor issues that users frequently overlook while communicating with the practitioner. It will establish an environment in which users can feel safe and

secure in sharing their difficulties without fear of being judged by others. The Homoeopathic Chatbot allows physicians and patients from all over the world to keep in touch.

With the aid of medical APIs, healthcare is one of the most relevant industries where chatbots may be used to determine specific prescriptions and medical advice for clients. However, there have been no advancements in the use of chatbot platforms in homeopathy-based treatment protocols because of things like the existence of multiple homeopathic repertories, the intricacy of the repertories (particularly BCCR), the established use of repertory-based proprietary software by homeopathic doctors, and the sparse use of IT solutions in homeopathic practice.^{10 11}

If a Chatbot mimics all of the features of an instant messaging system, it can be incredibly efficient and simple to use. Chatbots are primarily text-driven, with iconography and coherent widgets that make interacting with a bot simple. This program seeks to study the current e-healthcare structure, which entails a complex interaction with human machines and presents an alternative method: a chat interface created and configured to act and communicate with patients as if they were human people. Chatbots are classified into two types: non-intelligent chatbots that use predefined human-written dialogue flows and intelligent AI chatbots that use machine learning³.

In this situation, chatbots must be precise in differentially diagnosing the symptoms and able to map the patient's symptoms to the repertory to let the practitioner select the best drug from the list provided by the platform and present it to the patient.¹²

According to a national survey by ICMR, which covered 19 states and 35 districts across the nation, about 14% of sick people turned to ISM & H (Indian System of Medicine and Homeopathy), with 45,000 people from 33,666 households doing so. The low percentage of patients using ISM & H is attributed to the slow advancement and lack of practitioners in ISM & H. Patients, however, cited the inexpensive cost of care and fewer side effects as benefits of adhering to ISM & H. This illustrates the capacity of homoeopathy to reach the general public on par with allopathic medical techniques, which have been well-established through clinical and scientific experiments to show maximal efficacy and quicker recovery from illnesses despite the complex side effects on the patient.¹²

According to an NSSO 2014 poll, homoeopathy continues to be the treatment of choice for patients with chronic illnesses, older populations, and rural locations, making the goal even more optimistic and inspiring. Despite the practitioners having access to a sizable amount of homoeopathic repertory literature, manual referencing, listing salient medications based on the patient's medical condition, and prescribing appropriate medications mapped to thousands of symptoms is a difficult task that can be tiresome and time-consuming. Therefore, using a digital platform, particularly an interactive, chatbot-based tool, might increase the practitioner's work efficiency by reducing the amount of time spent manually enrolling prescriptions.¹³

Furthermore, the homeopath community is discouraged from using the software due to its high cost when compared to proprietary, practitioner-assisting homeopathic repertory software like Zomeo, Hompath Firefly, Dotphi, and Mercurius. This is because paying for the software would require charging patients, which would have a negative impact on their careers. The use of chatbot-based interactive applications, which can be created in an open-source environment and extend the reach of the homeopath's service to remote areas, may, on the other hand, lead to widespread application usage, making it easier for the patient and the practitioner to approach and diagnose each other.¹⁴ Medical chatbots have proven to be affordable, effective, and user-friendly depending on their sophistication and interactive design. Localized regional communities greatly benefit from chatbot apps that use NLP (Natural Language Processing) and ML (Machine Learning) that are focused on indigenous languages.¹⁵ As a result, patients may feel more at ease using medical chatbots that communicate with the doctor through an application. The practice of differential diagnosis, which is carried out by allopathic practitioners as well as by homeopathic practitioners utilizing repertories, can be accurately simulated by medical chatbots in real-time.¹⁵ Although chatbots in healthcare are still extremely young, their use and number are predicted to increase by 2029. According to a report, the medical chatbot market's revenue is predicted to increase between 2019 and 2029 at a compound annual growth rate of 26.29%.

PROPOSED MODEL:

The Homoeopathic medical chatbot engages with a patient by conducting an interview, comprehending their primary complaints in natural language, and submitting findings to doctors for additional investigation. Chatbot delivers a patient-end mobile application that proactively collects patient ailment narratives and background information; this can happen at any time before the doctor's appointment and in any location. The chatbot also includes a doctor-end desktop application that allows doctors to see their patients' information and interview results with repertorization. An analysis engine for comprehending detailed symptom descriptions provided by patients, such as location, sensation, modalities, and accompanying concerns (concomitants). Symptomatic mapper for speculating about possible reasons and a question generator for creating additional interview questions. Decrease the risk of losing crucial information in the interview reports. This also minimizes the risk of people avoiding medical attention owing to shyness or cultural differences. Furthermore, many studies have demonstrated that people are more honest when confronted with a robot rather than human health personnel. As a result, the chatbot is more likely to acquire accurate information about the patients.¹⁶ The medical chatbot that we describe in this article communicates with patients through the front end by gathering user information and medical symptoms, storing it in the Google Firebase cloud database, and using an algorithm that is programmed to map symptoms and medical problems to terms in the BBCR repertory, to generate a list of the top ten drugs that are then presented to the doctor for approval and prescription. We limit the functionality of our medical chatbot to symptoms related to illnesses of the Head that can be treated by homeopathic therapies due to the size of the BBCR repertory.¹⁷

**PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:
SOLUTION TO THE PROBLEM**

Fig 1: Shows Recommender System Design, a method of data collection by the patient's selected rubrics of the designed question format from location, sensation, and modalities. This collected data will be processed to the doctor by the medicine Database from the Head chapter of BBCR to provide probable graded remedies obtained through selected rubrics.

Fig.2: This diagram depicts the chatbot's operation from both the Doctor's and the Patient's perspectives.

CONCLUSION:

The integration of a Homoeopathic Chatbot represents a significant advancement in the field of homeopathic medicine. The article has outlined the challenges faced by practitioners in the existing methods of doctor-patient interaction and repertorization, emphasizing the need for a smart solution. The proposed Homoeopathic Chatbot serves as a promising model, addressing the limitations of manual repertorization and providing a user-friendly interface for both physicians and patients.

The article has extensively discussed the current landscape of medical chatbots, the existing homeopathic software, and the drawbacks of traditional repertorization methods. The suggested system design, shown in figures, offers a well-considered approach with the goals of improving remedy selection accuracy, streamlining the case-receiving process, and saving time for both practitioners and patients.

The proposed model gains credibility from the research undertaken on the viability of the Chatbot application, specifically utilizing Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics Repertory's "Head" Chapter. The goal of the Homoeopathic Chatbot is to transform the process of taking and repertorizing homeopathic cases by utilizing machine learning, artificial intelligence, and natural language processing. All things considered, the homoeopathic chatbot discussed in this article has the potential to revolutionize the practice of homeopathic medicine by providing a cutting-edge method for repertorization and case handling. Technology's continued essential position in healthcare makes the incorporation of such creative solutions promising for homeopathic practice's future.

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